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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Fiber optic Dosimetry for Low Energy prOton beAms (FIDEUA)</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA11-357</i>
General application	<i>RADNEXT WP5 research, Fiber-based dosimetry for radiation test facilities</i>
Type of test	<i>Radiation monitor calibration</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Sylvain Girard (UJM)</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Adriana Morana (UJM) Fiammetta Fricano (UJM) Luca Weninger (UJM)</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>25-28 November 2024</i>
Facility	<i>CNA</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>40 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The main goal of the FIDEUA test campaign was to evaluate the potential of fiber optic dosimeters, based either on the radiation induced attenuation (RIA) or on the radioluminescence (RIL) to complement existing monitoring solutions for low energy (~1 MeV – ~18 MeV) proton beams. For this, we used the latest technologies of radiation sensitive optical fibers developed at UJM such as miniaturized tapered optical fibers and dosimeter architectures. The outcomes of this project will benefit different research domains such as proton-therapy beam monitoring, diagnostics development for PetaWatt class laser and radiation tests.

Fiber-based dosimetry offers key advantages for implementation in radiation-rich environments, one of those being their capability to monitor the total ionizing dose (TID) or dose rate from different types of particles, such as electrons, protons, neutrons and photons. We can classify them into two families: the ones exploiting the RIA phenomenon to monitor the dose (fluence) and the one exploiting the RIL phenomenon to monitor the dose rate (flux). UJM is developing new architectures of optimized dosimeters to improve the performances in terms of dose or dose rate operation range, threshold sensitivities... One setup was used to assess the performances of RIA dosimeters under low energy (~15 MeV) proton exposures using optimized acquisition chains, comprising one optical source (either in visible or IR) and detectors. They differ in the targeted applications. For RIL-based dosimeters a photomultiplier tube allows measuring the RIL from a short fiber length (1 to 2 cm) exposed to the proton beams. An important aspect is that Geant4 simulations reveal that the different standard-size fibers can monitor proton of energies down to ~3 MeV (confirmed by recent CLPU results described in TA08-222 FIBILA report) and that lower energies can be achieved with the recent tapered (reduced in size from 125 to 10µm) optical fibers achievable by our team (DOI: [10.1109/JSEN.2023.3316773](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2023.3316773), see Fig1-2 for more details)

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Experiment test report

This report illustrates the results obtained with the RIL-based dosimetry at one of the two CNA facilities: the Cyclotron (15 MeV protons). Full results will be submitted for publication in the near future. In both cases, we used the experimental setup illustrated below (Figure 1) in order to measure the radioluminescence of the short length of radioluminescence optical fiber (a few cm) exposed to the proton flux at room temperature (RT).

Figure 1. Illustration of the experimental setup used to measure the radioluminescence from a set of optical fibers diversely doped at both the Cyclotron and Tandem facilities. For the Tandem, the use of a fibered vacuum feedthrough was needed to access the vacuum chamber.

Figure 2 illustrates the experimental configuration during an irradiation run at the Cyclotron using the 15MeV proton beam.

Figure 2. Picture of the test setup at the CNA Cyclotron facility.

Different tests have been conducted varying the flux and fluence deposited on different types of optical fibers. For each optical fiber type, two samples are characterized simultaneously, the first one is noted as 'pristine' meaning that it was never exposed to radiations before the CNA campaign, the second one as 'pre-irr' as the sample was pre-irradiated with X-rays up to a TID of 250 kGy before the irradiation campaign. It is known that the pre-irradiation is able to improve the dosimetry properties of the material

by reducing some parasitic effects such as the Bright Burn Effect (BBE) and the afterglow effect. Figure 3 illustrates the measured time evolution of the RIL of two samples of Ce-doped optical fibers (pristine and pre-irradiated) during 4 different runs associated with varying proton fluxes.

Figure 3. Illustration of the RIL kinetics of two Ce-doped fibers (pristine and pre-irradiated) during 4 runs at different fluxes at the CAN facility.

From these results, we could make a first analysis. First, the two fibers show similar RIL kinetics showing that the two independent dosimeters provide similar flux monitoring. The pre-irradiated optical fiber has a larger sensitivity than the pristine one. This is expected as the pre-treatment allow to reduce the trapping of charges by deep traps, enhancing the overall efficiency of the radioluminescence process. Figure 4 compares the normalized responses of the two fibers allowing to show the very good agreement between the proton flux monitored by the two dosimeters.

Figure 4. Illustration of the normalized RIL kinetics of two Ce-doped fibers (pristine and pre-irradiated) during 4 runs at different fluxes at the CNA facility.

By analysing all the results acquired during the multiple runs on the two optical fibers, it is possible to plot the calibration of the optical fiber that correlates the RIL intensity (expressed as a number of counts) and the proton flux (Figure 5) or proton fluence (Figure 6) as provided by the CNA facility. To obtain this last calibration curve, the RIL is integrated over the run time.

Figure 5. RIL calibration curve: RIL vs 15 MeV proton flux (flux provided by CNA facility)

Figure 6. RIL calibration curve: RIL vs 15 MeV proton fluence (fluence provided by CNA facility)

An important outcome of this set of experiments is that the fiber is extremely sensitive to the low energy protons (as it is in fact sensitive to the TID), the results have been obtained by attenuating a lot the RIL levels to not saturate the photomultiplier tube. As a consequence, the fibers are perfectly adequate for the monitoring of the low flux of this beam, a task that remain a challenge for CNA facility.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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